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Research on Friction stir welding using Taguchi method

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摘要

与文献中报道的传统焊接技术相比，搅拌摩擦焊接工艺是一种先进的焊接技术，具有许多优点。简而言之，这些优点。1.焊缝质量好2.功率消耗减少3.没有助焊剂或填充材料，等等。这种FSW工艺被认为是研究项目，因为它的优点和FSW工艺在各种汽车和航空工业中的日益普及。在这项工作中，报告了工艺参数的影响，如工具转速、焊接速度和倾斜角度对利用固态焊接技术搅拌摩擦焊的不同等级的铝合金的反应和拉伸强度的影响。对焊点进行了极限拉伸强度（UTS）和布氏硬度（BHN）的测试。采用田口方法获得最佳工艺参数，然后进行方差分析测试，找出影响极限拉伸强度和布氏硬度值的贡献和最重要的工艺参数。

关键词。搅拌摩擦焊，方差分析，极限拉伸强度，布氏硬度值，FEM，田口方法，HIS方法。

ABSTRACT

When compared to conventional welding techniques reported in the literature, the friction stir welding process is an advanced welding technique that offers numerous advantages. In a brief, the advantages: 1. Good weld quality 2. Power consumption is decreased 3. No flux or filler material, etc. This FSW process is considered as the research project because of its advantages and the growing popularity of the FSW process in various automobile and aerospace industries. The effects of process parameters such as tool rotational speed, weld speed, and tilt angle on the responses and tensile strength in dissimilar welding of Aluminum alloys of various grades utilizing the solid-state welding technique Friction Stir Welding are reported in this work. The weld joint was tested for ultimate tensile strength (UTS) and Brinell hardness number (BHN). Taguchi method was used to obtain the optimum process parameters and then ANOVA test was carried out to find the contribution and most significant process parameter effecting the ultimate tensile strength and Brinell hardness number.

Keywords: Friction stir welding, ANOVA analysis, Ultimate tensile strength, BHN, FEM, Taguchi method, HIS method.

1. Introduction

Friction stir welding (FSW) is a solid-state joining process, which was invented and patented by The Welding Institute (TWI) of Cambridge, United Kingdom in 1991. FSW is a solid phase welding process in which the metal to be welded is not melted during the welding, thus the crack and porosity often associated with fusion welding processes are eliminated. It combines frictional heating and stirring motion to soften and mix the interface between two workpieces. The FSW process uses no outside (filler) material, no shielding gases, and requires low energy input when compared to other welding processes. The grain structure in the weld zone is finer than that of the parent material and has similar strength, bending, and fatigue characteristics. The basic principle of the FSW process is shown in figure 1.1. The parts to be welded are placed on a backing plate and clamped in such a way that prevents the adjacent joint faces from being forced apart.

Figure 1.1 Schematic representation of friction stir welding process

A thermo mechanical model of the friction stir welding process was recreated in this study, and a surrogate model-based optimization approach was used to find the best process parameters. Zhu and Chao developed the thermomechanical model for friction stir welding of 304L stainless steel that was chosen for implementation. The selected finite element model was replicated in ANSYS®. The process was then simulated using the validated model. The effect of various input parameters such as heat input, welding speed, and clamping location on temperature distribution and residual stress in the workpiece was investigated using a design of experiments and parametric study. Finally, constrained optimization models were used to calculate mechanical properties of welded Al plates as a function of weld speed and rotational speed. Statistical techniques are often used to reduce the number of experiments conducted. As well as in the results we worked with the Taguchi method come with a new design called orthogonal array used to obtain a necessary information by an experiment frequency that is less than the factorial experiment without loss of the main data, and with the ANOVA analysis a statistical tool used to help decision-making by detecting any differences in the average performance of collections of items which are tested, the later introduced the signal to noise ratio, S/N, between the average response value caused by control factors and variability as consequence of noise factors.

2. Methods

A finite element modeling of the SFA process using multiphysics couplings to perform the interaction of the thermal properties of the process is done, generating volumetric mesh and border identification for the definition of the relevant

Models for the solution through numerical analysis.

The physical properties of the materials are defined as well as the process conditions for starting up the numerical solution, by entering as parameters a tool rotation speed of 1000 RPM, a holding time of 10 s and a room temperature of 25 °C.

The physical properties of the material for the joints and tool are shown in Table 3.1 and 3.2.

Table 3.1 Physical Properties of Aluminum AA1100

F_e	S_i	$C_p(\text{J/kg K})$	$\sigma_y(\text{MPa})$	$K(\text{W/m K})$	$T_f(K)$	Espesor(mm)
0.95	0.95	904	120	220	916	6

Table 3.2 Physical Properties of H13 Steel

$P(\text{kg/m}^3)$	$C_p(\text{BTU/hr ft } ^\circ\text{F})$	$E(\text{GPa})$	$K(\text{W/m K})$
7750	17	207	27

a. Taguchi method

As an improved method of design of experiments, the Taguchi method, developed by Dr. Genechi Taguchi. Taguchi in the late 1940s, is widely used in manufacturing processes, material design and development, and geometry design. A routine set of tools in the Taguchi method includes orthogonal arrays, ANOVA, and the S/N ratio.

b. Orthogonal Arrays

Orthogonal arrays are fractional factorial designs, yield a minimum number of experimental runs. The

sign of an orthogonal array with the same number of levels l for all m factors is $LN(lm)LN(lm)$, where N is the total number of experiment runs and L is Latin squares. When the level sizes of different factors, such as, when m_1 factors have l_1 levels and m_2 factors have l_2 levels, $LN(lm_1 l_2 m_2)LN(l_1 m_1 l_2 m_2)$ is indicated. The first is known as a pure orthogonal array, whereas the last one is called as a mixed-level orthogonal array. Each level of one factor in each column occurs equally in one orthogonal array with a strength of t , and the combination of levels in t factors occurs equally. Additional details are described in other works.

c. Analysis of variance (ANOVA)

ANOVA is a statistical method used to quantitatively assess the significance of factors to responses and their confidence. The sum of squares, degrees of freedom, mean square, F value, and percent contribution of the factor are all used to assess the significance of a factor. The total sum of squares (subscript T), which is calculated using all of the observed values for different factors, measures the overall variability of data:

where l is the number of levels, n_i is the number of runs at i th level, y_{ij} is the value of j th observation at i th level, and \bar{y} is the mean of all observations.

The sum of squares for each factor (subscript f) is given by:

$$SS_f = n_i \sum_{i=1}^l (\bar{y}_i - \bar{y})^2 \quad (3.2)$$

where \bar{y}_i is the mean of observations at the i th level.

Subtracting the sum of SS_D of all factors from SS_T leads to:

$$SS_D = SS_T - \sum_{k=1}^m SS_f(k) \quad (3.3)$$

where m is the total number of factors and k is the index referring to a factor. SS_D is the sum of squares of the deviation (subscript D).

The degrees of freedom of each factor, DoF_f , is equal to $(l - 1)$ when the number of its level is l .

The mean square for each factor (subscript f) is

$$MS_f = \frac{SS_f}{DoF_f} \quad (3.4)$$

and the mean square of deviation is

$$MS_D = \frac{SS_D}{DoF_D} \quad (3.5)$$

where DoF_D is the degrees of freedom of deviation (subscript D) given by:

$$DoFD = N - 1 - \sum (lk - 1) m \quad k=1 \quad (3.6)$$

where N is the total number of run

The F-statistic value of each factor is calculated using the equation below,

$$F = \frac{MS_f}{MS_D}$$

(3.7)

Afterwards, the obtained F value can be compared with the corresponding critical value, $F_{\alpha}(DoF_f, DoF_D)$ at the $(1-\alpha)$ confidence level in the F distribution. If the calculated F value is larger than the critical value, the probability of correctly accepting the null hypothesis is $(1-\alpha)$. The percent contribution of each factor is defined as:

$$C = \frac{SS_f}{(SS_T - SS_D)} \times 100\%$$

(3.8)

d. Signal to Noise (S/N) ratio

The S/N ratio is extensively used as a quality index, rather than being merely associated with the signal and noise. Three S/N ratio representations are shown in Equations (3.10)–(3.11): smaller-the-better, nominal-the-best, and larger-the-better. For all representations, a higher S/N ratio is desirable. In the present work, the smaller-the-better equation is used to evaluate the thermal and thermomechanical responses because the equation treats the smallest value of responses as the best quality.

Smaller-the-better: S/N $= -10 \log \left(\frac{1}{n_i} \sum_{j=1}^{n_i} y_{ij}^2 \right)$

(3.9)

Nominal-the-best: S/N $= -10 \log \left(\frac{1}{n_i} \sum_{j=1}^{n_i} (y_{ij} - \bar{y}_i)^2 \right)$

(3.10)

Large-the-better: S/N $= -10 \log \left(\frac{1}{n_i} \sum_{j=1}^{n_i} \frac{1}{y_{ij}^2} \right)$

(3.11)

Here n_i is the number of runs at the i th level, y_{ij} is the value of the j th observation at the i th level, and \bar{y} is the mean number of observations at the i th level of a factor.

3. Results and discussions

a. Tensile test and hardness test

The tensile test was performed by using the UTM machine [model UTM-60]. There were nine specimens were made from each friction stir welded samples. The specimens were cut perpendicular to the direction of weld.

Figure 3.6 Tensile test specimen

Figure 3.7 Specimen after tensile test

The data obtained by tensile test is tabulated in table 3.3. The hardness test was performed on the Brinell hardness testing machine. It was performed at the center of the stir zone using 100 Kgf load and 10 mm hardened steel ball indenter. The obtained Brinell hardness number is tabulated in table 3.3.

Table 3.3 UTS and BHN for different process parameters

Exp. No.	Input parameter		Response parameter	
	Welding speed (mm/min)	Rotational speed (rpm)	Ultimate tensile strength (MPa)	Brinell hardness number
2	30	1400	175.0	43
3	30	1500	175.0	45
4	40	1300	162.5	44
5	40	1400	187.5	48
6	40	1500	175.0	46
7	50	1300	137.5	39
8	50	140	162.5	43
9	50	1500	150.0	42

b. Optimization by Taguchi method and ANOVA test

For obtaining the optimum process parameter, Taguchi method was used to find the signal to noise ratios. The Larger-the-Better criteria were used for UTS. The S/N ratio was calculated by using the given formula:

$$S/N \text{ ratio} = -10 \log \left(\frac{1}{n} \sum \frac{1}{y^2} \right) \quad (3.18)$$

Where n is number of observations and y is observed data. The S/N ratios obtained by using Minitab 18 software is tabulated in table 3.4.

Table 3.4 Tabulated S/N ratios for UTS

Welding Speed (mm/min)	Rotational Speed (rpm)	Ultimate tensile strength (MPa)	S/N Ratio
30	1300	162.5	44.21707

30	1400	175.0	44.86076
30	1500	175.0	44.86076
40	1300	162.5	44.21707
40	1400	187.5	45.46003
40	1500	175.0	44.86076
50	1300	137.5	42.76605
50	1400	162.5	44.21707
50	1500	150.0	43.52183

Figure 3.8 S/N Ratio plot for different input parameter

Figure 3.9 Interaction plot for UTS

From fig.3.7, it is clear that the optimum FSW parameter for UTS is 1400 rpm and 40 mm/min. Now, the optimum response can be predicted by using formula:

$$\phi = \frac{T}{n} + \left(\gamma_{WS2} - \frac{T}{n} \right) + \left(\gamma_{RS2} - \frac{T}{n} \right) \quad (3.19)$$

Where T/n is overall mean of tensile strength, γ_{WS2} is avg. tensile strength of 2nd level of welding speed, and γ_{RS2} is avg. tensile strength of 2nd level of tool rotational speed. The predicted value for UTS is:

$$\phi = 165.28 + (175 - 165.28) + (15 - 165.28) = 184.72 \text{ MPa} \quad (3.20)$$

The maximum value of UTS obtained in the experiment was 187.5 MPa. Hence, experimental value of UTS is deviated by 1.50% from the predicted value.

Now, applying ANOVA test for understanding the effect of factors on the UTS. The ANOVA test was done by using Minitab 18 software and results for UTS are tabulated in table 3.5.

From table 3.5, it is clear both welding speed and rotational speed is significant and percentage contribution shows the relative power of factor to reduce the variance.

- Hardness

The larger-the-better criteria is also used for Brinell hardness number and the S/N ratios are tabulated in table 3.6.

Table 3.5 Analysis of Variance for UTS

Source	DF	Adj SS	Adj MS	F Value	P Value	% Contribution
Welding Speed (mm/min)	2	1076.39	538.19	31.00	0.004	59.62
Rotational Speed (rpm)	2	659.72	329.86	19.00	0.009	36.54
Error	4	69.44	17.36			3.84
Total	8	1805.56				100

Table 3.6 Tabulated S/N ratios for BHN

Welding Speed (mm/min)	Rotational Speed (rpm)	Brinell Hardness Number	S/N Ratios
30	1300	41	31.2557
30	1400	43	32.6694
30	1500	45	33.0643
40	1300	44	32.8691
40	1400	48	33.6248
40	1500	46	33.2552
50	1300	39	31.8213
50	1400	43	32.6694
50	1500	42	32.4650

Figure 3.10 S/N Ratio plot for different input parameter

Figure 3.11 Interaction plot for BHN

From Fig.3.9, the optimum input parameter for BHN is 1400 rpm and 40 mm/min. Now, the optimum response can be predicted by using formula:

$$\varphi = \frac{B}{n} + \left(\mu_{WS2} - \frac{B}{n} \right) + \left(\mu_{RS2} - \frac{B}{n} \right) \quad (3.21)$$

Where B/n is overall mean of tensile strength, μ_{WS2} is avg. Brinell hardness number of 2nd level of welding speed and μ_{RS2} is avg. Brinell hardness number of 2nd level of tool rotational speed. The predicted value for BHN is

$$\varphi = 43.44 + (46 - 43.44) + (44.67 - 43.44) = 47.43 \quad (3.22)$$

Table 3.7 Analysis of variation for BHN

Source	DF	Adj SS	Adj MS	F Value	P Value	% Contribution
Welding Speed (mm/min)	2	33.556	16.778	15.10	0.014	57.63
Rotational Speed (rpm)	2	20.222	10.111	9.10	0.032	34.73
Error	4	4.444	1.111			7.64
Total	8	58.222				100

From table 3.7, it is clear both welding speed as well as rotational speed is significant for Brinell hardness number.

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